

Conductance Studies of Tetraalkylammonium Bromides in Dimethylsulphoxide + Water Mixtures at 25°

SUSANTA DAS and D. K. HAZRA*

Department of Chemistry, North Bengal University, Darjeeling-734 430

Manuscript received 10 September 1987, accepted 22 December 1987

Conductance measurements have been reported for tetraalkylammonium bromides, R_4NBr ($R = CH_3 -$ to $C_6H_5 -$) in the concentration range 0.005–0.08 mol dm⁻³ in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO)+water mixtures (20, 40, 60 and 80 wt% of DMSO) at 25°. The data have been analysed by the Fuoss conductance equation and the characteristic parameters Λ_0 , K_A and R have been evaluated. The single ion conductances (λ_0) have been determined using the 'reference electrolyte' Bu_4NBPb_4 . The analysis of the data indicates that the electrolytes are not associated in these solvent mixtures. The ionic Walden products have been determined and its variations with the solvent compositions discussed. The results have been explained in terms of ion-solvent interactions and structural changes in the solvent mixtures.

STUDIES on the transport properties of electrolytes in different solvents are of great importance to obtain formations on the behaviour of ions in solution¹. Recently, much importance has been given to the study of electrolytes in different dipolar aprotic solvents as they have proved to be useful for various electrochemical investigations²⁻⁴.

The interactions of the hydrophobic side chains of quaternary ammonium halides with water have been studied conductometrically by Evans and Kay⁵. Arrington and Griswold⁶ studied the conductances of tetraalkylammonium halides in DMSO to understand their behaviour in non-aqueous solvents. The conductometric studies of tetraalkylammonium salts in DMSO+H₂O mixtures would enable us to understand the ion-solvent interactions and other structural changes that may occur due to the addition of the aprotic co-solvent DMSO to water. Moreover, the variation of the Walden product with solvent composition can also be properly ascertained from such studies. These considerations led us to undertake the present conductometric studies of tetraalkylammonium bromides in DMSO+water mixed solvents at 25°.

Experimental

The purification of DMSO (Baker, A.R.) and tetraalkylammonium bromides (Fluka, Puriss) was carried out as described in earlier communication⁷. Triple-distilled water (specific conductance, $< 1 \times 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) from all-glass distilling unit was used. Freshly distilled solvents were always used for solution preparation.

Solvent mixtures were prepared by weight. A stock solution for each salt ($\sim 0.1 M$) in the appropriate solvent mixture was prepared by weight and the working solutions were obtained by weight

dilution. The molar concentrations (0.005–0.08 M) of the solutions were calculated from molarity and density values. The viscosities of solvents mixtures were taken from our works and the density was determined using an accurate pycnometer. The solvent properties are given in Table 1. The dielectric constants of the solvent mixtures were taken from the literature⁸. Conductances were measured in a Pye-Unicam PW 9509 conductivity bridge at 2000 Hz using a dip-type cell (cell constant 0.730 cm⁻¹) and having an accuracy of $\pm 0.1\%$. The measurements were carried out in a thermostat at $25 \pm 0.01^\circ$.

TABLE 1—SOLVENT PROPERTIES OF DMSO+ WATER MIXTURES AT 25°

DMSO wt%	D	η_0 poise	d_0 g cm ⁻³
0	78.3	0.008 9	0.997 1
20	77.4	0.013 4	1.023 4
40	75.9	0.022 2	1.059 1
60	72.4	0.034 5	1.082 5
80	65.3	0.034 4	1.098 1
100	46.7	0.020 0	1.096 1

Results and Discussion

The equivalent conductances at infinite dilution (Λ^0) and the association constants (K_A) were calculated using the Fuoss⁹ conductance equation,

$$\Lambda = P[\Lambda^0(1 + RX) + EL] \quad (1)$$

$$P = [1 - \alpha(1 - \gamma)] \quad (2)$$

$$\gamma = 1 - K_A C \nu^2 f^2 \quad (3)$$

$$-\ln f = \beta k/2(1 + kR) \quad (4)$$

$$\beta = \frac{e^2}{\epsilon k T} \quad (5)$$

$$K_A = K_R/(1 - \alpha) = K_R(1 + K_S) \quad (6)$$

where, R_X and EL are relaxation and hydrodynamic terms respectively as derived by Fuoss and other terms have their usual significance. The parameters Λ° , K_A and R were obtained by solving the above equations. The calculations were performed on a Wipro Z-650 computer using the programme furnished by Fuoss. Initial Λ° values for the iteration procedure were obtained from Shedlovsky extrapolations of the data.

In practice, calculations were made by finding the values which minimise,

$$\sigma^2 = \sum_j [\Lambda_j(\text{cal}) - \Lambda_j(\text{obs})]^2 / (n-2) \quad (7)$$

for a sequence of R values and then plotting $\sigma\% = 100 \sigma / \Lambda^\circ$ against R , the best fit R corresponds to the maximum in the $\sigma\% - R$ curve. However, since the coarse scan using unit increment of R value from 4 to 15 gave no significant minimum in $\sigma\% - R$ curve, the computations were done by fixing R at $\beta/2$. The Λ° values and the association constants (K_A) obtained are given in Table 2. The corresponding Λ° values in water and DMSO have been included from the literature^{5,6} for the purpose of comparison.

The variations of Λ° values of $R_4\text{NBr}$ salts with solvent composition are shown in Fig. 1. It can be found that the Λ° values of tetraalkylammonium bromides decrease as the alkyl chain length increases (Table 2). This is in agreement with the earlier findings in several pure and mixed solvents¹⁰ and is attributed with the size and structure-forming effect of the cations¹¹ (anions being the same). For

Fig. 1. Variation of limiting equivalent conductance (Λ°) with composition of solvent mixtures: (1) Me_4NBr , (2) Et_4NBr , (3) Pr_4NBr , and (4) Bu_4NBr .

any particular electrolyte, the Λ° values continuously decreasing with the addition of DMSO, pass through a minimum around 60–80 wt% of DMSO and then increase with further addition of DMSO. The Λ° values decrease with the increase in viscosity (η_0) of the solvent mixtures but the Walden product have been found to be different. However, the maximum in η_0 almost coincides with the region of observed minima in Λ° . The results indicate that the hydrodynamic entity is of importance in both cases but the difference in solvation of ions is responsible for the change in the mobility of ions and hence Λ° .

The addition of DMSO to water first enhances the three-dimensional structure of water; the subsequent addition of DMSO leads to the breakdown of water structure but with concomitant formation of $\text{DMSO} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ complex. The maximum structuredness seems to occur at ~33 mol% of DMSO due to the formation of $\text{DMSO} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}^{12-14}$ complex and after this the disruption of the complex takes place. The continuous increase in η_0 of solvent mixtures and decrease in Λ° values of salts with a maximum and minimum around 33 mol% of DMSO, respectively, suggest that the hydrodynamic entity increases continuously upto 33 mol% of DMSO but decreases afterwards. It is expected that the tetraalkylammonium ions are strongly solvated by water. Addition of DMSO increases the size of the hydrodynamic entity which becomes maximum at 33 mol% (Λ° -minimum) after which the dehydration of ions would take place. However, the nature of solvation will vary from ion to ion. Thus the differences in values of a particular electrolyte in different solvents must be due to the difference in mobilities of the ions at infinite dilution.

The association constants (K_A) are very low for all the electrolytes in DMSO+water mixtures (Table 2) and the values pass through a maximum around 60 wt% of DMSO and may be ascribed to the selective solvation of cations and anions by DMSO in the mixed solvents. The selective solvation of $R_4\text{N}^+$ ions by DMSO prevents the approach of Br^- ion near $R_4\text{N}^+$ ion and in effect such a low K_A value.

The variation of the Walden product ($\Lambda^\circ\eta_0$) (Fig. 2) with solvent composition is different for different salts. The $\Lambda^\circ\eta_0$ values of $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NBr}$ (Table 1) pass through a maximum at 40 wt% of DMSO. For $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{NBr}$, the maximum lies in the region 20 wt% of DMSO. However, two maxima are obtained at 40 and 80 wt% of DMSO for $(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)_4\text{NBr}$, and at 20 and 80 wt% of DMSO for $(\text{C}_4\text{H}_9)_4\text{NBr}$.

The Λ° and Walden products of the salts were split into the corresponding ionic components using Bu_4NBPh_4 as the 'reference electrolyte'. Bu_4NBPh_4 was obtained from the relationship: $\text{Bu}_4\text{NBPh}_4 = \text{Bu}_4\text{NBr} + \text{NaBPh}_4 - \text{NaBr}$. The ratio $\lambda_{\text{Bu}_4\text{N}^+}^\circ / \lambda_{\text{BPh}_4^-}^\circ$ was taken^{10,17} as 1.07. The ionic conductances (λ_i°) and ionic Walden products are given in Tables 3 and 4. λ_i° (Table 3) decreases as we go

Fig. 2. Variation of Walden product ($\lambda_{\pm}\eta_0$) with composition of solvent mixtures: (1) Me_4NBr , (2) Et_4NBr , (3) Pr_4NBr , and (4) Bu_4NBr .

TABLE 2—CONDUCTANCE PARAMETERS OF TETRAALKYL-AMMONIUM BROMIDES IN DMSO+ WATER MIXTURES AT 25°

DMSO wt%	Λ° $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	K_A $(\text{mol dm}^{-3})^{-1}$	$\beta/2$	$\sigma\%$	$\Lambda^\circ\eta_0$ $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ poise
Me₄NBr					
0	122.67	—	—	—	1.092
20	90.86(±0.26)	1.95	3.62	0.14	1.218
40	55.60(±0.17)	1.39	3.69	0.16	1.235
60	30.57(±0.40)	3.97	3.87	0.42	1.055
80	27.55(±0.04)	3.76	4.29	0.19	0.948
100	42.66	—	—	—	0.853
Et₄NBr					
0	110.57	—	—	—	0.983
20	79.15(±0.03)	0.97	3.62	0.07	1.061
40	46.29(±0.17)	2.20	3.69	0.37	1.028
60	29.75(±0.08)	3.87	3.87	0.16	1.026
80	26.59(±0.25)	3.17	4.29	0.33	0.915
100	41.12	—	—	—	0.822
Pr₄NBr					
0	101.47	—	—	—	0.908
20	69.03(±0.27)	1.22	3.62	0.22	0.925
40	42.79(±0.08)	2.87	3.69	0.11	0.950
60	24.06(±0.24)	4.90	3.87	0.25	0.831
80	24.25(±0.19)	4.12	4.29	0.26	0.878
100	37.95	—	—	—	0.760
Bu₄NBr					
0	97.56	—	—	—	0.868
20	67.91(±0.26)	3.99	3.62	0.30	0.910
40	40.39(±0.19)	4.52	3.69	0.17	0.897
60	22.05(±0.21)	5.39	3.87	0.08	0.761
80	24.25(±0.05)	4.56	4.29	0.13	0.834
100	35.65	—	—	—	0.713

from Me_4N^+ to Bu_4N^+ in DMSO+water mixtures and is in accordance with the fact that the size and hydrophobic solvations in water and binary mixtures increase in the sequence, $\text{Me}_4\text{N}^+ < \text{Et}_4\text{N}^+ < \text{Pr}_4\text{N}^+ < \text{Bu}_4\text{N}^+$. The change is only marginal initially but decreases to pass through a minimum at ~80 wt% except for Bu_4N^+ where the minimum is observed at 60 wt%. The bromide ion is a structure-breaker in water and is also poorly solvated by DMSO due to steric factor¹⁸ and the minimum in λ° is obtained at 60 wt% of DMSO. The maximum in the viscosity of DMSO+water mixtures gives rise, as required by Walden's rule, to a minimum in the ionic mobilities around 60 wt% of DMSO.

TABLE 3—SINGLE IONIC CONDUCTANCES (λ°) IN DMSO+ WATER MIXTURES AT 25°

DMSO wt%	λ° ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)				
	Me_4N^+	Et_4N^+	Pr_4N^+	Bu_4N^+	Br^-
0	44.42	32.32	23.22	19.31	78.25
20	44.51	32.33	22.71	21.59	46.32
40	23.86	14.55	11.05	8.65	31.74
60	16.83	16.01	10.32	8.31	13.74
80	12.09	11.13	9.68	8.79	15.46
100	18.60	17.06	13.89	11.59	24.06

TABLE 4—IONIC WALDEN PRODUCTS ($\lambda_{\pm}^\circ\eta_0$) AT INFINITE DILUTION IN DMSO+ WATER MIXTURES AT 25°

DMSO wt%	$\lambda_{\pm}^\circ\eta_0$ ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ poise)				
	Me_4N^+	Et_4N^+	Pr_4N^+	Bu_4N^+	Br^-
0	0.395	0.287	0.207	0.172	0.696
20	0.597	0.440	0.304	0.289	0.621
40	0.580	0.323	0.245	0.192	0.705
60	0.580	0.552	0.356	0.287	0.474
80	0.416	0.983	0.333	0.303	0.592
100	0.372	0.341	0.278	0.232	0.481

The ionic Walden products, $\lambda_{\pm}^\circ\eta_0$, for the tetraalkylammonium ions show two maxima at 20 and 60 wt% of DMSO (at 20 and 80 wt% in case of Bu_4N^+). The Walden product of bromide ion almost continuously decreases with the addition of DMSO. Though the quantitative explanation of the variation of the Walden product with solvent composition is not exactly known but it can be suggested from the results that these ions are solvated to different extents in these solvent mixtures. As the Walden product of an ion is inversely proportional to the effective radius of the ion in a solvent, the initial variation in the Walden products of tetraalkylammonium ions in DMSO+water mixtures can be explained in terms of selective solvation of R_4N^+ ions by DMSO and water molecules, respectively. The decrease in the Walden products of R_4N^+ ions after 60 wt% of DMSO indicates the preferential solvation of R_4N^+ ions by DMSO in DMSO+water mixtures. In case of bromide ion the present results is not indicative of selective hydration of this ion by water.

In the present studies it is thus apparent that the variations of Walden products with solvent compositions are due to the variation of electrochemical

equilibrium between tetraalkylammonium ions and the solvent molecules on one hand and the selective solvation of ions on the other hand with the composition of mixed polar solvents.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of a Fellowship to one of them (S. D.).

References

1. J. PADOVA in "Water and Aqueous Solutions-Structure, Thermodynamics and Transport Processes", ed. R. A. HORNE, Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1972.
2. A. J. PARKER, *Quart. Rev.*, 1962, **16**, 168.
3. W. C. KURVILN, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 1965, **9**, 1099.
4. J. N. BUTLER, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1966, **14**, 89.
5. D. F. EVANS and R. L. KAY, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, **70**, 366.
6. D. E. ARRINGTON and E. GRISWOLD, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1970, **74**, 123.
7. S. DAS, D. K. HAZRA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Z. Phys. Chem. (N. F.)*, 1983, **138**, 185.
8. "Physical Chemistry of Organic Solvent Systems", eds. A. K. GOVINGTON and T. DICKINSON, Plenum New York, 1973, p. 19.
9. R. M. FUOSS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1978, **82**, 2427.
10. Ref. 8, Chap. 5.
11. L. BAHADUR and M. V. R. MURTI, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1980, 1409.
12. D. D. MACDONALD and J. B. HYNÉ, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1971, **49**, 611.
13. D. D. MACDONALD, J. B. HYNÉ and F. L. SUINTON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **92**, 6355.
14. J. J. LINDBERG and J. KENTTAMMA, *Soumen. Kem., B*, 1960, **33**, 104.
15. B. S. KRUMGALZ, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1983, 571.
16. B. S. KRUMGALZ, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1980, 1275.
17. D. S. GILL and M. K. SEKHRI, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1982, 119.
18. W. YANG-WN in Ref. 1, Chap. 15.